

**DECEPTION, and
DISINFORMATION, MEDIA
DOMINION**

**MARCOSIAN
DISSOLUTION to the
COMMUNICATORS
of the PAST and the
PRESENT**

The
RIPPLES
of the

Deception, Disinformation, and Media Dominion: The Ripples of the Marcosian Dissolution to the Communicators of the Past and the Present

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Introduction

Use a pen wisely and it becomes an instrument, abuse it and it becomes a threat. It can either drive progression or wreak havoc — communication simply flows as the ink does through the cartridge, following the commands of its wielder.

In the ever-changing landscape of communication, it flourishes and evolves with the people wielding it. It constantly flows through the mold of the economy, politics, and culture of their community through the course of history. In these communities, people in authority influence the production and dissemination of information, carrying significant weight on the system of representation in platforms, the construction of personal and collective identities, and intercultural communication.

A notable period in history that has contributed a discernible impact on media and communication in the past and in the present is the Marcos administration. During martial law, the circulation of information was heavily controlled by the government. By silencing the competing voices and establishing a media outlet under his authority, the government was able to suppress public criticism and any voice in opposition to theirs. This problem has negatively impacted the Filipino community's mass communication process and media content representation.

Continuing the narrative to the present Marcos administration under President Ferdinand Marcos Jr., disinformation and media domination remained prevalent despite the increase of freedom in media and communication. This can be observed in different forms of contemporary platforms like Facebook, one of the main sources of information in the Filipino community as proven by the conducted study of the Ateneo School of Government. According to Mateo (2022), the study reported that 78.8% of the respondents obtain their news from Facebook feeds, with two in every three respondents stating that they pay attention to government and politics related content on the mentioned platform despite the risks of fake news.

In an interview by Devlin (2022) from BBC News, a social media troll hidden by the name Jon managed hundreds of fake profiles and Facebook pages for his politician clients and their campaigns. He is a part of the disinformation systems that aim to boost support for these clients even through the methods of falsehoods. This is only one of the many deceptions and misuses of media and communication in contemporary times.

In addition to this, the report covered by research specialist and digital forensics Pauline Macaraig on disinformation in the Philippine elections 2022 demonstrated how Marcos' group penetrated the Facebook platform and benefited from it. In order to change the narrative or modify public perceptions of his family and their crimes against the Filipino community, President Marcos Jr., the late dictator's son astutely made use of the platform. They have coordinated posts and pushed narratives regarding the supposed Marcos administration legacy over the years leading to the 2022 elections with the tracked data existing as early as 2014 (Bernido, 2022).

This presents the significant challenge of deception, disinformation, and media dominion being faced by the Filipino community considering the Marcos administration's stimulus on media and communication.

Synthesis Objectives

In addressing the communication-related problem for our paper titled “ Deception, Disinformation, and Media Dominion: The Ripples of the Marcosian Dissolution to the Communicators of the Past and the Present” our insights, learnings and knowledge that we have impart to every module will help address it properly. As part of the lessons that we have learned in COMM 10 is the media convergence in which it tackles the maximizing and efficiency of using media in communication and information technology. In line with this, there is a dialogic relationship that we establish between the new and old media that we have during the regime of Marcos. Since during the term of Marcos under the Martial law the media is silenced and controlled by him.

As cited in an article “FAST FACTS: How Marcos silenced, controlled the media during Martial Law”(Elemia, 2020), He attacked the press freedom during his term as dictator in the following ways:

- Shutting down every print media
- Arresting media owners and journalists
- Rejecting foreign journalists
- Marcos-controlled media
- News and information censorship

The information that we have stated above clearly shows how Marcos controlled the media during his term of dictatorship. In contrast, today in our society, his son is the President of the Philippines in which there is a rampant problem in our media: the historical distortion, historical revisionism and circulation of fake news and disinformation. Resulting in inaccurate information and making people to be a fake news peddler. Moreover, in addressing the problems in the media like fake news, historical distortion and revisionism. Here are some ways

(LibGuides: Keepin' It Real: Tips & Strategies for Evaluating Fake News: Fake News, 2017): First, we must verify the information and readings that we share and we also think before sharing it. Second, we debunk the fake news by reporting it on the media platforms that we used and by fact-checking the information and evaluating it. Third, is to expand the information that we see and read. We should not limit ourselves on the information that we only see on TikTok or on YouTube. We should expand the network of sources that we used. Last, is to evaluate the news and information we see by comparing the content we see on various online platforms and cross-check it with other resources.

Furthermore, in the second module we have learned about communication and rhetoric. It elucidates that rhetoric is an art of persuasion involving deliberate use of language on influencing our feelings, actions, and thoughts as an individual. Moreover, we also gain knowledge in line with rhetorical situations that includes elements like: exigence, audience, constraints and political rhetoric. Exigence is an imperfection defect obstacle in which the problem that is dealing in a situation can be changed or influenced. For the audience, it is simply the persons who are capable of being influenced by the discourses and can be the mediator of change in a particular rhetorical situation. Meanwhile, for the constraints this are the people, events, objects, and relations that has a power on influencing the decisions and actions of the audience in modifying the exigence. Additionally, the political rhetoric as cited by the lecture video of Sir Kneel is concerned with the strategies used in constructing the messages in debates and disputes as persuasive type of messages (Condor, et al, 2013).

The concepts of ethos, logos, and pathos as Aristotle means of persuasion. In connection with our topic in this synthesis paper, we would like to emphasize on the two events in Philippine History which call for our ethical and moral judgment and it calls for our knowledge on utilizing what is a political rhetoric. During the time of Martial Law in the administration of the dictator Marcos. These historical events call for our ethical and moral judgment because we perceive these historical actions as inappropriate. To further elaborate on this matter, the group would like to discuss the martial law during the era of Ferdinand Marcos Sr. During the inhumane presidency of the dictator's regime, he abused his power which resulted in human rights violations, and press freedom was suppressed. A lot of innocent people were tortured and killed and injustice during those time is rampant and visible the reason that the extrajudicial killings during the years of Marcos's presidency are almost exceeding to 3,256 people and 35,000 people are tortured and some people became political prisoners, victims of torture, and Desaparecidos.

Additionally, 70,000 people are being arrested/detained for unreasonable cases and they are unfairly imprisoned. Aside from inhumane killings and violations of human rights, we must never forget that the dictator plundered and stole billions of money in our nation and that the Presidential Commission on Good Government is still recovering the money of Marcoses ill-gotten wealth. We must never forget all these sufferings and abuses of the Marcos Regime. This martial law period calls for ethical and moral judgment that we perceive as inappropriate. With this historical past that we have encountered let us be reminded on the political rhetoric topic and let us use our knowledge and insights that we gain on module 2 to not forget the past.

Besides the first and second module, we also have more succeeding modules to 3-5. In module 3, it is about positioning ourselves in our community. Not just that but it is also about our

identity, culture, environment, beliefs, traits, characteristics, traditions, and values that molds us an effective communicator in our community as an individual and part of this society. As a part of the society and an Iskolar ng Bayan or Iska / Isko, we would like to help address communication issues today in the Marcos regime by amplifying the voices of those who cannot speak for their rights and political discourse since they are afraid of the government. We would also like to immerse ourselves with the masses and be with them in fighting for their rights. A lot of social issues we are currently experiencing in this regime. Being an "ISKOLAR NG BAYAN" means to us in a literal perspective that you are studying by the means of our taxes and the people's taxes. Iskolar ng Bayan is not just about guaranteed free education and service excellence by providing quality education through taxes. Still, it is more about the importance and significance of a student that fights against oppression and tyranny and amplifies the voices of the people that do not have a voice in fighting injustices. It is not only academic-wise and beyond academically excellent, but also by giving and serving the society in the community where we belong.

Moreover, our identity as being an Iskolar ng Bayan means having the heart and the mind to serve the Filipino people and your community through knowledge, skills, dedication, and commitments. In connection with that, we obtained on filling them with justifiable, right, and good services that we could offer in the betterment of the bayan or the whole community that can make a significant factor on humanity specifically to the lives of people and to justify their rights and needs. Iskolar ng Bayan is about you doing everything for the bayan. We thrive and do our very best to serve our fellow students and the masses, and marginalized people by offering ourselves by participating in the community. Also, in doing charitable works, being an advocate, volunteering to help people, and fighting for misinformation and disinformation by keeping the masses informed and choosing to fight, speak and represent the masses and be constantly on the right side in fighting the struggle and societal problems in this Marcos administration. What matters most and the true essence of Iskolar ng Bayan in this time that red-tagging is rampant is all about the matter of being with the masses and immersing and interacting ourselves with them by sharing solidarity with them and not by losing hope and being scared of the current administration. May we always remember that being an Iskolar ng Bayan is in all ways and always that we uphold honor and excellence everywhere we go and serve the people well.

For the fourth module, it is about the work of representation, semiotics, and the class in the media. With those lessons we made an output on examining a media personality that represents the identity and personality of our community. As a member of this group, I, Rachele examine Leni Robredo for the output that I made in module 4 for I believe that she represents the community that I belong to in UP Baguio. Leni Robredo portrays my identity in the community and my community as a mighty woman that is full of hope in life. She possesses traits like a caring, decent public servant, and most importantly, she has transparency and accountability as a politician that our country needs. Moreover, as cited by an article titled "The Role of Transparency and Accountability for Economic Development in Resource-rich Countries," addressed by Agustín Carstens. He is a Deputy Managing Director of the International Monetary Fund; transparency and accountability are needed to foster social well-being in the economy of a society. People who have powers in the community, like politicians, have a duty to public authorities, and they are responsible for ensuring the transparency of everything they do and the information they share in a community. Unlike the current administration we have now in Marcos-Duterte they do not possess this transparency and accountability characteristics.

Furthermore, accountability and transparency are two things that cannot separate since only accountability can achieve transparency. Suppose the politician does not possess the trait of being transparent and accountable. In that case, it will lead to less economic growth, and corruption will hinder the growth and expansion of a community and its people. Just like what we are currently experiencing in the current administration in which people suffer on public transportation and the prices of the products. Aside from those things, I considered my community here in the UP System, specifically in UP Baguio. Most students and people like Leni since she has excellent credentials, abilities, and desire to serve the people and unites every person by promoting a safer society and community that we all deserve. Additionally, as a part of this community as students we take part on ground and participate in fighting what is right and as we support Leni Robredo, we aim also to address disinformation and historical revisionism that is rampant in our community and to stop red tagging. Since activism is not terrorism. We also never forget the past and the historical records of the family of Marcoses. "FAKE NEWS" and "DISINFORMATION" is the issue also in the Social Media that misrepresent Leni Robredo; it includes the rumors, disinformation, and fake news that circulate online and on social media in her personal life and as a politician. Furthermore, those fake news consist of the following:

- Vlogger's claim that Angat Buhay is competing with Marcos Jr.'s gov't NEEDS CONTEXT
- Videos MISLEAD, imply Robredo will be jailed over COA flagging
- Robredo-led OVP did NOT 'hide P25M' from COA
- FALSE FB posts claim Robredo caught sleeping in airport lounge
- Robredo DID NOT threaten chaos if she loses, has NO alliance with NPA

To read every article, please can the QR codes:

QR Codes for the articles mentioned. Source: VERA FILES FACT CHECK

Last but not the least we have module 5. In this module we learned about intercultural communication, verbal, and nonverbal codes in different intercultural communication situations. Moreover, for the objectives of the synthesis includes the following:

- To explore the changing landscape of communication from the martial law period of the Marcos administration until the present, including the evolving mass communication process and media convergence.

- To examine how the Marcos administration and its supporters used persuasion techniques such as ethos, logos, and pathos to win votes and support.
- To study the representation of the Marcos administration and related issues in newspapers and social media.
- To consider the role of intercultural communication and verbal and nonverbal communication in the context of local and global forces that influence intercultural interactions, including history, way of life, experiences, social and political positions.

Discussion of Communication Concepts: First Module

The use of phrases such as "primitive" and "savage" to refer to certain cultures has been a longstanding and old practice in anthropology, as seen in works like *The Savage Mind* by Claude Lévi-Strauss, *Les Fonctions mentales dans les sociétés inférieures (How Natives Think)*, and *La Mentalité primitive (The "Soul" of the Primitive)* by Lucien Lévy-Bruhl, and *The Mind of Primitive Man* by Franz Boas. With their repetitive usage, a negative connotation forms within the context of these words and are treated to highlight a perceived deficiency in the culture being referred to, like the term "illiterate." However, in recent years there has been a shift towards a more positive understanding of oral cultures and the oral-literacy contrast. Lévi-Strauss himself has upheld and represented these "primitive" societies against the charge that their minds are of a "coarser quality" or profoundly separate to that of the literate man. He suggests replacing the term "primitive" with "without writing," though this phrase that he proposes still contains a bit of a pessimistic nuance and indicates Lévi-Strauss's leaning towards chirographic (writing) bias.

In the readings of the first module, it is suggested that a better substitute to the phrases that are stated above is "oral." Lévi-Strauss's statement that *"the so-called primitive societies have a mental structure which is not only different from ours but is equally valid, equally complex, equally rich"* highlights the importance of acknowledging the validity and richness of all cultures. Lévi-Strauss's assertion that "the savage mind totalizes" can be understood as the belief that oral cultures tend to view the world as a cohesive whole. However, orality is not a lesser form of communication and should not be viewed as such. The terminologies of "primitive" and "savage" can be harmful and limiting to those that are being portrayed with the given words, as they can lead to a biased and narrow interpretation of other cultures that are foreign to the observer. Refusing to use these types of terms and instead going to observe how their language penetrates to their culture will then recognize the complexity and value of all cultures. Adopting a more respectful and inclusive approach to cultural differences can facilitate greater understanding and cooperation among individuals from diverse backgrounds.

It is also important to consider the ways in which oral and literate cultures have influenced one another throughout history. For example, the advent of print culture, which brought written language to a new level of prominence, was influenced by both oral and literate cultures. Similarly, the current electronic culture, which builds upon both written and print cultures, is also influenced by both oral and literate traditions. Understanding these relationships

is crucial for understanding the evolution of human society and the ways in which communication and information transmission have changed over time.

The notion of nationality and unity within diversity is a pertinent one for Filipinos, as our nation has undergone significant evolution over the centuries. As an archipelago comprising many various tribes and cultures, the Philippines has been subject to various changes and influences, mostly due to invasions and colonization by foreign powers. The Philippines, a nation located in Southeast Asia, has a complex history marked by both independence and occupation. The country's prolonged colonization by the Spanish resulted in the heavy influence of Spanish culture and language, while the later American occupation brought with it American culture and values. This blend of Spanish and American cultures can still be seen today in the mix of native words with Spanish roots and American borrowed words that have been Filipinized, as well as the presence of American English as one of our two national languages. Notwithstanding these influences, the Philippines has maintained its rich cultural heritage and built its own unique identity.

The photos of Claude Lévi-Strauss, Franz Boas, and Lucien Lévy-Bruhl.
(Sources: Wikipedia and Encyclopedia Britannica)

As demonstrated heartily by the country after formally gained independence in 1946 after the Second World War, during which it was invaded by Japan. Despite this, the Philippines was able to maintain its sovereignty and continue to develop as a society and its continual expansion as a functional society in Southeast Asia. Today, it is a diverse and vibrant country that has retained its cultural heritage while also embracing new influences and ideas. However, the Philippines has also had to cope with internal issues, such as the corrupt regime of Ferdinand E. Marcos Sr. in the 1970s and the recent re-introduction of his son into the highest seat of government, as well as the spread of deception, disinformation, and media domination. These challenges pose fundamental questions about the nature of power, autonomy, and identity in the Philippines, making it a valuable analysis for reflection in this current synthesis paper.

Oral cultures rely primarily on spoken language for communication, while literate cultures rely on written language. This difference has major associations for the way in which

information is transmitted and understood. In oral cultures, for example, information is often conveyed with storytelling, an efficacious means of communicating complex ideas in an appealing and memorable way. In contrast, literate cultures tend to rely on written texts to transmit information, which can be more precise but may also be bleak and problematic to remember. Another aspect of that in the first module, is the understanding of the evolution of these cultures over time. Preceding works in this field associated oral cultures with alphabetic writing systems, rather than other types of writing systems. The development of writing allowed for the creation of the legal system, and the preservation of knowledge and cultural traditions in written form.

Headline photos of various news from SMNI News, a channel known for promoting misinformation, is a result of a religious company commercializing the media.
(Source: SMNI News Channel on YouTube)

With advancement of technologies over the years and the Philippines also being exposed to globalization, Filipino media has been affected, which led to an international exchange of

media products and ideas. This has resulted in the enrichment of media in the country, as well as the possible homogenization of media content, which can be used to spread foreign cultural values and disrupt the local values of the country, which can cause a new form of imperialism. The increasing commercialization of media, known as hypercommercialization, has led to a focus on profit over public interest and an increase in sensationalism. Concentration of media ownership and the globalization of media companies have also been identified as challenges to the mass communication process. The proliferation of technology has also changed the nature of the audience in mass communication, leading to audience fragmentation and the targeting of specific groups through niche media and addressable technologies. This trend towards individualized media consumption may have an impact on national culture and the collective cultural experience, hypothetically leading to the contraction of cultural experiences and the disruption of the storytelling role of media.

Right now, the evolution of digital media in the Philippines has changed the structure and operation of media industries. New business models, such as subscription services like Netflix and freemium models like Spotify, have emerged and disrupted traditional hierarchically structured media organizations. The use of algorithms to personalize content and target ads has also raised concerns about media industries influencing public discourse and potentially amplifying biased or misleading information. This trails back to the seemingly questionable remarks of the international community with the return of the Marcoses as the top dog of the government, and the dissolution of the idea of decent leadership, something that ostracized the Marcoses before. Now that we are in the digital age, the credibility of online sources, recognition, media responsibility, and the struggle against misinformation is important for Filipinos to understand such changes to mitigate the threat of media illiteracy, and to know the truth.

Some of the popular social media applications in an Android device.
(Source: Clever Clicks Digital)

Discussion of Communication Concepts: Second Module

The second module covers the idea of *rhetorical situation*, which refers to the context in which *a rhetorical discourse* takes place. Although the presence of rhetorical discourse often indicates the existence of a rhetorical situation, it is not always the case that a situation only exists when there is discourse, or vice versa. A rhetorical situation involves more than just the context of a speech, or the presence of an audience and a communicative goal. It is also distinct from a persuasive situation, in which the audience is swayed by the speech. According to the reading by Lloyd Bitzer, rhetoric is always intended to persuade in this sense. The reading also mentions Bronislaw Malinowski's study of primitive language, which presents the concept of "*context of situation*," which aligns with the idea that rhetorical situation is a natural context made up of people, events, objects, relationships, and an exigence that strongly prompts an utterance. This prompted utterance naturally contributes to the situation and is necessary for the completion of situational activity, and it obtains its meaning and rhetorical character through its interaction with the situation. Bitzer uses the example of a fishing expedition to demonstrate this concept, with the situation encompassing the objects, people, events, and relationships involved in the hunt, and the governing exigence being the success of the hunt. This situation dictates the observations and responses made and limits the words spoken in the same way that it limits physical actions. Additionally, Bitzer suggests that verbal responses to the requirements of the situation are functional and necessary in the same way that physical responses are.

Bitzer further argues that rhetorical situation is the foundation or basis for rhetorical activity, whether it is a simple, primitive utterance or a more complex, artistic discourse. To say that rhetoric is situational means that rhetorical discourse emerges as a response to a situation, that the situation gives rhetorical significance to the discourse, that a rhetorical situation is a necessary condition for rhetorical discourse, and that the situation controls the rhetorical response. It is recommended that the situation, rather than the rhetor or persuasive intent, is the source and basis for rhetorical activity and criticism. Bitzer classifies rhetorical situation as a grouping of people, events, objects, and relationships that shows an actual or potential exigence that can be addressed through discourse. The exigence is one of the three elements of a rhetorical situation, along with the audience to be inspired in decision and action, and the constraints that affect the rhetor and can be applied to the audience. A rhetorical situation can be understood as a context in which there is a need or opportunity for discourse to address an exigence and impact the decision or action of an audience. Like exigence, it is a burning need or problem that necessitates attention. Still, not all exigences are rhetorical. A rhetorical exigence is one that can be altered through discourse, or communication. In a rhetorical situation, there is usually at least one controlling exigence, which serves as the organizing principle and specifies the audience and the desired change. The controlling exigence may be perceived plainly or ambiguously, and it may be real or illusory, significant, or inconsequential. It may also be traditional or new. When it is acknowledged and is robust and vital, it can change the ideas or opinions and actions or

behaviors of those who are cognizant of it and may persuade them to respond rhetorically if they are able to do so.

In a rhetorical situation, the audience is a key role. It is the people who are influenced by discourse and serve as agents of change. On the contrary, the audience partaking in the sciences or artistic use of literature don't have to be rhetorical audiences, as they can gain knowledge or take part in experiencing the aesthetic of science and poetic language. Every rhetorical situation includes constraints, along with exigence and audience, that act as the circumstances that bear upon decision-making and action. Constraints in this sense include beliefs, attitudes, documents, facts, traditions, interests, and motives. In the reading, there are two main types of constraints: those that are originated or controlled by the rhetor and their method (artistic proofs), and those that exist within the situation (inartistic proofs). Both types of constraints can be further divided into those that are proper and those that are improper. When a rhetor enters a rhetorical situation and generates and begins discourse, they become additional elements in this situation.

Rhetorical discourse is created in response to a rhetorical situation, which is a pressing need or problem that requires attention and can be altered through discourse. A rhetorical situation's power can be observed if it is possible to predict the types of discourse that will be spawned in retort. They invite fitting responses, those that are fit and can play a part in it, positively modifying it. On the flip side, responses that do not fit the given situation are not rhetorical. The purpose of it is to bring about change by shaping the judgements and activities of the audience. It is characterized by a sense of urgency and a desire to modify the exigence, often employing ethical and emotional appeals and stylistic patterns. The success of rhetorical discourse depends on the fit between it and the situation, as well as the usefulness of the discourse in persuading the crowd.

The photos of Lloyd Bitzer and Bronislaw Manilowski. (Source: Wikipedia)

To answer in a rhetorical discourse, one must participate in the rhetorical response. A rhetorical response is one that satisfies the requirements of the situation in which it is used. The situation in this context can be empirically studied and is often based on historical or real events. It can give out the purpose, theme, and style of the response. A noteworthy differentiation is a must between actual rhetorical situations and those that are manufactured or imaginary. Fictive situations, such as those found in literature, may become genuine rhetorical situations when they are used as a response to a real situation. Likewise, situations can be either simple or complex, and they can be either highly structured or loosely structured. Such a situation includes only some elements that ought to interact, meanwhile, a complex situation encompasses many elements that must interact.

A situation is completely structured when all elements are located and prepared for the task, while it is said to be inaccurately structured when its elements are less organized. Situations may turn out to be weakened in structure due to convolution or disjunction, like when the demands in the situation are too many or the audience is dispersed by some other force or unaware of its responsibilities and powers. Rhetorical situations can evolve to a point where a rhetorical response is fitting, and then may either decay or persist. Some situations recur and may generate similar responses over time, leading to the emergence of established rhetorical forms and traditions. These forms and traditions can then function as constraints on new responses in that form.

Ultimately, rhetoric is a discipline that is justified by its capacity to facilitate positive change in the world through discourse. It differs from the field of persuasion, which may be studied scientifically but lacks the philosophical foundations of a practical discipline. In an ideal world, there would be no need for rhetoric, but in the real world, there are many exigences or situations that call for change using rhetorical communication with a mediating audience.

Discussion of Communication Concepts: Third Module

The third module focuses on *identity*, a concept that has long been studied in the social and behavioral sciences as a way of understanding how people think and act. Within psychology, identity is often seen as an important aspect of self and self-concept that gives meaning to people's sense of self. In sociology, identity is often understood as *the social roles that people play*, which helps to explain how social position can influence a person's sense of self. More recently, scholars have started to focus on the association between identity and communication, recognizing that communication plays a role in shaping and negotiating a person's identity. This can include both self-reflection and discourse as well as the influence of ascribed identities and identity negotiation in social interactions. These approaches to studying identity highlight the close connection between communication and identity and the way that communication can shape and influence a person's sense of self.

The notion of personal identity refers to how an individual see themselves and how this self-perception is shaped by external factors. There are various psychological theories that examine this concept, including the "*looking glass self*," *Self-Verification Theory*, *Control Theory*, *Identity Theory*, and *Self-Discrepancy Theory*. The personal-relational identity gap combines these ideas and indicates that others' appraisals are internalized and become a part of an individual's identity, and that discrepancies between self-concepts and internalized others' appraisals can be created and negotiated through communication.

There is also the concept of personal-enacted identity gap, which refers to the discrepancy between an individual's self-views and the identities they express in communication. This gap can be caused by various factors, and theories such as Goffman's dramaturgical approach, Petronio's *Communication Boundary Management Theory*, and Jack's *Silencing the Self Theory* explore different aspects of this discrepancy. According to CTI, personal-enacted identity gap includes both active and passive expressions of self and aims to understand the implications of these discrepancies for identity and communication outcomes.

Identity gaps can impact on communication satisfaction, feeling understood, and conversational appropriateness and effectiveness. Communication satisfaction is influenced by whether an individual's inner standards are reinforced by their own communicative behavior and others' appraisals. When there is an incongruity between an individual's personal identity and the individualism they express in communication (personal-enacted identity gap) or when there is a discrepancy between an individual's personal identity and how they think others see them (personal-relational identity gap), they may not feel satisfied with the communication. Similarly, feeling understood is impacted when individuals have problems voicing their authentic selves (personal-enacted identity gap) and may lead to misunderstandings and a personal-relational

identity gap. Finally, conversational correctness and efficiency can also be influenced by identity gaps, as individuals may perceive their communication as not being effective and their behavior as violating the rules for achieving desired appraisals.

Topics that constitute the concept of identity. (Source: Pixabay)

In one of the readings, the *Communication Theory of Identity (CTI)* is explored and is a defined as a theory that investigates the close relationship among identity and communication, viewing identity as communication rather than simply being a product of interaction. According to CTI, entities affect social roles and affairs through exchange, and then act out their identities through communication. Identity is seen as having multiple loci or frames, including personal, relational, enacted, and collective identities, which are interconnected and constantly negotiated and co-constructed through communication. Previous research on CTI has often focused on individual frames instead of examining how they operate jointly. The present study aims to explore the concept of interpenetration in CTI, develop instruments to measure "identity gaps" as an aspect of interpenetration, and examine the relationships between identity gaps and communication outcomes to test the conceptualization of identity gaps and an assumption of CTI.

CTI recognizes that identity has multiple loci or frames, including personal, relational, enacted, and communal identities, which can operate separately or be interpenetrated or

integrated. The construct of "identity gaps" has been proposed to define discrepancies between or among these frames. This study focused on two specific identity gaps: one between personal and ascribed relational identities, and the other between personal and enacted identities. The personal-relational identity gap refers to discrepancies between an individual's personal identity and their perception of how others view them, while the personal-enacted identity gap refers to discrepancies between an individual's personal identity and their expressed or performed identity. Results of Jung and Hecht's study revealed strong negative correlations between the identity gaps and three communication outcomes: communication satisfaction, feeling understood, and conversational appropriateness and effectiveness. These findings encourage the idea that identity gaps are a communicative phenomenon and that there is a close relationship between identity and communication, as proposed in CTI.

Jung and Hecht examined the concept of identity gaps to understand the dynamic interrelationships among the four frames of identity proposed in CTI. The results showed strong negative correlations between the identity gaps and three communication outcomes: communication satisfaction, feeling understood, and conversational appropriateness and effectiveness. The path analyses also suggested that the personal-enacted gap may have a causal effect on the communication outcomes, while the personal-relational gap may be an outcome itself or caused by the communication outcomes. These findings support the idea that identity gaps are a communicative phenomenon and that there is a close correlation between identity and communication, as proposed in CTI.

Discussion of Communication Concepts: Fourth Module

Semiotics, also known as **semiology**, is the study of signs and symbols and how they are used to communicate meaning. It was formally developed by Ferdinand de Saussure in Switzerland and is concerned with the way language shapes human perception and thought. At its core, semiotics is about the relationship between the **signifier**, which is the physical form of the sign, and the **signified**, which is the mental concept it represents), which is called signification. **Denotation** refers to the identification of a sign, while connotation refers to the associations and feelings that a sign evokes in a person. Saussure's concept of langue, or a language system, is organized along two axes: the **paradigmatic axis**, which refers to the vertical set of associations, and the syntagmatic axis, which refers to the horizontal, or sequential, arrangement of signs. In semiotics, signs are divided into three main categories: **iconic**, **index**, and **symbolic**. **Iconic signs** bear a resemblance to what they represent, **index signs** have a direct, causal relationship to what they represent, and **symbolic signs** are arbitrary and rely on a consensus about their meaning. Roland Barthes introduced the concept of the "**mythical sign**," which is a sign that has become so deeply ingrained in a society's ideology that it is no longer seen as a sign, but rather as a natural part of the world. **Binary oppositions**, or contrasts between signs that have meanings that operate in opposition to one another, are powerful in shaping the meanings of signs. Examples of binary oppositions include town and country, man and woman, and civilization and savagery. These oppositions are often structurally related to each other and function to order meanings, creating myths about urban and rural life, for example. Semiotics

can be used to analyze images and media language and is an influential discipline in media studies.

As introduced earlier in the last paragraph, the semiotic approach is expanded upon by Roland Barthes. In his essay *Myth Today*, Barthes argued that representation can occur at two levels: the level of denotation, in which the elements of an image are decoded into their corresponding concepts to form a sign with a simple, literal message, and the level of connotation, in which this completed message or sign is linked to a second set of signifieds, creating a broader, culturally framed meaning or myth. He used the example of a magazine cover featuring a black soldier saluting the French flag to illustrate this process and applied the concept of myth to advertisements, arguing that they can use commodities to signify national identity or "ness." However, later developments in cultural studies and the work of philosophers like Derrida and Foucault have recognized the necessarily interpretive nature of culture and the fact that *interpretations are always followed by other interpretations, resulting in an endless chain of meaning*. These later theorists also focused on the production of social knowledge and power dynamics in the production of representations.

Michel Foucault's approach to representation focused on the production of knowledge through discourse, which refers to the rules and practices that produce meaningful statements and regulate discourse in different historical periods. He believed that in each period, discourse produced different forms of *knowledge, objects, subjects, and practices of knowledge*, and that these were specific to their *historical and cultural context* and could not exist outside specific discourses. He also emphasized the relationship between *power* and *knowledge*, and how power operates within institutional apparatuses and their technologies to regulate the conduct of others. According to Foucault, power is not centralized or monopolized by a single source, but rather circulates through a network-like organization that permeates all levels of social existence. This means that power relations exist at every site of social life, including both the private and public spheres, and are not just present in the form of repression but are also productive, creating things like discourse, knowledge, and pleasure. He argued that power is not something that is simply imposed on individuals, but rather that individuals also have a role in its production and maintenance. Later theories of representation also focused on issues of power and knowledge, including the ways in which dominant groups use representation to maintain their power and the ways in which marginalized groups use it to challenge dominant narratives and assert their own identities.

The photos of Ferdinand de Saussure, Roland Barthes, and Michel Foucault.
(Sources: Encyclopedia Britannica, Famous Philosophers, and TheFamousPeople.com)

These theories also recognized the necessarily interpretive nature of culture, which is open to interpretation and is constantly changing as it is reinterpreted by different individuals and groups. The concept of representation is described as a form of social action that has the power to shape and reinforce social norms and values and is not simply a reflection of reality. The role of power and knowledge in the production and interpretation of representations is also emphasized, as well as the ways in which dominant groups use representation to maintain their power and marginalized groups use it to challenge dominant narratives and assert their own identities. The example of this is Foucault's book, *The Order of Things*, discusses the painting Las Meninas by Velasquez and its representation of the nature of representation. The center of the painting features the *Infanta Margarita*, surrounded by her entourage, while everyone's gaze is directed towards the front of the painting at unseen sitters, who are eventually revealed to be the King and Queen in a mirror on the back wall. Foucault uses this painting to argue that there is no one fixed or final meaning to the painting, and that the reflection in the mirror represents what is lacking in everyone's gaze.

Discussion of Communication Concepts: Fifth Module

In the contemporary context of globalization, intercultural communication has become complex due to the expanding diversity brought about by the movement of people from different cultural backgrounds into closer proximity with one another. Advances in transportation and communication technology have facilitated this process, allowing people to connect and interact with one another in both physical and virtual spaces. Yet, globalization has also changed to inequalities and cultural conflicts, as some individuals and groups have greater access to and privilege within the global system while others struggle to meet basic needs. Differences in cultures are turning to be more prominent, resulting to conflicts and inequalities, with escalating disparities amongst the rich and the poor within and between countries. Environmental problems, like climate change, also disproportionately impact people from different cultural backgrounds.

The reading in the module describes cultural studies as a transdisciplinary field that aims to critique social inequalities and work towards social change, with a particular focus on analyzing and critiquing power relations and understanding the historical and political context of intercultural relations. In this context, the concept of culture is increasingly seen as a way of referring to dimensions of difference that express and mobilize group identities, rather than as a stable, coherent entity. Culture is often seen as something that can be used for economic and political gain and is often turned into a commodity by global organizations to successfully examine and engage with the cultural aspects of globalization, it is important to understand how culture is impacted by and impacts global economic, political, and social dynamics.

Positionality is an important concept in intercultural communication that refers to the impact of an individual's social and power relations on their perspective and understanding of the world. Standpoint theory, a theory related to positionality, speculates that people from

marginalized groups have a unique perspective that can deliver an inclusive understanding of the world. It is established on the idea that those who are subordinated must recognize both their own perspective and of those in strength to endure. It also highlights the connection between power and knowledge, and the potential for marginalized groups to challenge and contradict systems of oppression through their distinctive viewpoint. Knowledge about the concept of positionality can be useful in intercultural communication in order to recognize and avoid the destructive impacts of power imbalances, such as cultural imperialism and the hassle of dominant cultural norms and values.

Intercultural communication is inspired by anthropology, particularly that of the works of Edward T. Hall and Clifford Geertz. Hall focused on the micro level of human interaction, mainly nonverbal communication, while Geertz emphasized the role of symbols in understanding culture as a system of shared meanings passed down through generations and expressed through symbols. Culture is a system of symbols that enables groups of people to communicate and understand life. Symbols acquire meaning through their relationship within a culture and create a system of meanings. It shapes how people think, feel, and behave in different situations. Norms, which are rules for appropriate behavior, and cultural values, which are ideas about what is important or desirable, are key elements of culture that influence communication. On the other hand, culture is honed by historical, social, and political forces. It is important to consider the cultural influences on communication and to be aware of one's own cultural perspective.

Proceeding to another reading made by Maggay, the culture of communication in a Filipino context, within a particular society is examined. The society in question relies heavily on the use of hints and signs to communicate indirectly, but also has specific words and phrases that are used for direct communication in informal or intimate settings or in formal contexts for exchanging ideas. Additionally, the use of intermediaries to convey sensitive messages and the disclosure of hidden information are both major characteristics of the culture's communication practice. The language used in direct responses and discussions, as well as during social gatherings where news and gossip are shared, is also explored. The cultural significance of eloquent rhetorical styles and phonetic traditions is also noted.

The photos of Edward Hall, Clifford Geertz, and Melba Maggay.
(Sources: Communicationsinsider.weebly.com, Quotesgram, and CBE International)

It delves into the concept of hints, which can be both verbal and non-verbal. These hints are often used in situations where the speaker feels sensitive or embarrassed and may involve the use of evasive or flowery language. The role of mediators, particularly in conflict situations, is also discussed as a means of avoiding direct communication. Mediators act as intermediaries, conveying messages between parties who may not be willing or able to communicate directly. Various types of messages can be conveyed through a mediator, including requests, instructions, and greetings. These messages are often rooted in the social reality of the parties involved and represent their perspectives or interests.

The text also examines the way Filipinos communicate and express their feelings, noting specific words and phrases that allow for the direct revelation of thoughts and emotions. The concept of "*fruit-covering*," or the act of hiding one's true feelings to maintain social decorum, is also introduced. The concept of "*palabas*," or the presentation of a false or misleading appearance to achieve a particular goal, is also discussed. The reading suggests that there is a clear distinction in Filipino culture between what is true and what is pretended to be true, and that it is important to be aware of this distinction to fully understand the underlying meanings of external communication.

In general, Filipinos tend to use indirect and ambiguous language in communication, and the level of directness is often affected by the social distance and status of the participants. However, there are also mechanisms for resolving misunderstandings and conflicts, and context is important in communication in the Philippines. The use of rhetorical devices in speech is also common in Filipino culture. This emphasizes the different methods in which Filipinos communicate and the cultural norms and practices that influence these communication styles. Recognizing these traits can assist individuals in effectively communicating with Filipinos and gaining a deeper understanding of their perspectives and viewpoints.

Output Insights: First Module

Gaining a deeper understanding of the differences between oral and literate cultures can help us to appreciate and respect the diversity of human cultures and ways of thinking. Exploring the contrast between orality and literacy can provide valuable insights into the evolution of human society and the way we think and express ourselves. This has been reflected on by the group on the topic of media convergence.

The group's insights emphasizes that both traditional and new media are beneficial tools for individuals within a particular community, as they enhance literacy and communication skills. Both types of media have analogous features that facilitate communication and information dissemination. In terms of power, both traditional and new media can wield influence and impact by providing knowledge and understanding through the information they disseminate. Nevertheless, in terms of availability and openness, both media aim to provide equal access to information, but may use different platforms to do so.

The home page for the video streaming site, Netflix. (Source: Netflix)

The past few years have seen a significant shift in how information and entertainment are delivered, with all forms of media converging onto one device. The widespread availability of the internet and social networking sites has made it possible for anyone with a computer and an internet connection to potentially reach a large audience. However, the media industry is facing challenges such as media fragmentation and the concentration of corporations controlling mass media and the internet. The entertainment industry is also facing challenges, such as declining royalties for artists. Despite these challenges, the media's global reach and the empowerment of audiences through social technology offer the potential for positive change and the ability to provide solutions and value in new ways. This is explained in the first module as media convergence.

But first, what does media convergence bring into the table? According to the reading in the first module, it refers to the merging of traditional media forms, such as print, radio, and television, with digital media, such as the internet and mobile devices. It has always been driven by the digitization of nearly all information, the increasing speed and accessibility of networks,

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<p>Nisha Bedofa Marketplace, Collectible NFT LOWEST \$1.20 AVAILABLE 11/240</p>	<p>Idol Philippines Season 2 Golden Ticket Sep 10 Marketplace, Collectible NFT LOWEST \$4.00 AVAILABLE 24/50</p>	<p>Idol Philippines Season 2 Golden Ticket Aug 27 Marketplace, Collectible NFT LOWEST \$8.50 AVAILABLE 8/50</p>	<p>Tisha Gomez Marketplace, Collectible NFT LOWEST \$30.00 AVAILABLE 5/50</p>

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Web capture for Idol Philippines NFT on ThetaDrop, a move done by ABS-CBN Entertainment to follow to the trends of media convergence. (Source: ThetaDrop)

and advances in technology that allow devices to do more. As a form of response, media companies seek to achieve synergy by using multiple channels to deliver their content, and this has led to several mergers and acquisitions in the media and telecommunications industries. Audience fragmentation and the desire of audiences to access media anytime and anywhere have also contributed to the trend of convergence.

Trying to synergize with convergence has effects on the mass media industry, which is still currently experiencing a major shift due to the increasing use of the internet, digitization, and mobility. This has led to new producers finding new ways to deliver content to new audiences, causing turmoil within the industry. Audiences now have a wide range of options and are beginning to adapt to the changing media landscape. Entertainment companies are attempting to make all their content available on every platform, with presence being the key to a wider audience reach, but it is uncertain whether this strategy will be successful for long enough as there may be other factors that can affect said online presence, often presented as a clash of online culture versus the traditional media norm.

Trends of media ownership, which is not only happening in other countries, but also on our own turf, now leads to a decrease in the number of media companies and a narrowing of the range of information and entertainment available to the public. These cases pose a threat to the diversity of viewpoints and the free exchange of ideas, especially in a democratic country like the Philippines. Due to conglomeration, media outlets are owned by larger non-media companies that may have their own interests and agendas, which may include the spread of their form of religion or faith, having bias towards individuals who may or may not have done wrong, and wooing to the government on how the national news is to be broadcasted. This can influence the coverage of media outlets and the public policy decisions that affect them, potentially leading to media companies prioritizing profit over quality journalism and covering senseless stories or cover-ups, rather than real issues in the country.

Consumers of media now have multiple ways to avail of these things, such as satellite radio, terrestrial radio, digital terrestrial radio, and streamed web radio. The release of media has also been ever-changing, especially with the recent pandemic dropping all physical sales hard, and that the world had to force itself to be online, which is a focal point when the first year of the pandemic started. Nowadays, movies can be released in theaters, on video-on-demand, on video rental, and for download simultaneously, as well as being released directly to web downloading sites, video-on-demand services, and video streaming sites. The platform on which media is consumed is also a factor, with options including theaters, television, and streaming services, and the cost of each platform varies. In the coming years, audiences will be deciding how they prefer to consume media and how much they are willing to pay for it, and media literacy will be important in helping them make informed decisions.

Media consumption patterns have undergone a major change that has had a detrimental effect on various media sectors. For example, movie attendance has decreased, physical copies of recorded music have become less popular, and the video rental industry is now almost non-existent in many countries. Television viewing has also declined due to the rise of video sharing websites, which saw a surge in popularity during the pandemic. The console video game

industry has also struggled, with the emergence of personal computer and mobile games. Furthermore, the sale of printed books has decreased and both daily and Sunday newspaper circulation has declined. Though, the adoption of radio streaming on video streaming sites has helped to maintain a certain level of commercial radio listenership. This shows that both media industries and consumers face a range of challenges, which include fragmentation of audiences, new technologies, media ownership, globalization, and increased commercialization.

Video streaming of 99.5 Play FM. (Source: Play FM Twitch Channel)

The group learned about the relationship between media and communication and social factors such as politics and lifestyle. They discovered that people in positions of power and influence can shape the production and distribution of information, which can impact the representation of the community and influence how we perceive ourselves and others, shaping our individual and collective identities. The group also learned about the history of media and communication and how social factors have an impact on it, as well as the reverse relationship where communication can shape social factors. They learned about the role that influential people and those in positions of authority play in shaping information and representation, and how this influences the development of individual and collective identities within the community.

Output Insights: Second Module

In the second module explaining the purpose and significance of the discipline of rhetoric, Aristotle believed that a speaker's character, or *ethos*, can influence an audience's perception of their argument. In contemporary political rhetoric, the notion of *ethos* is often tied to the identity of the speaker. Some theorists reject the concept of a fixed identity, while others view it as a rhetorical production. In political communication, speakers may try to create a sense of shared identity, or consubstantiality, with their audience by presenting their arguments as

exercises in political consensus, appealing to in-groups, signifying consubstantiality as a future goal, or implicitly displaying allegiance using first-person pronouns.

Former President and dictator Ferdinand Marcos Sr. delivering a speech.
(Source: Harry S. Truman Library and Museum)

One way to address the problem of audience diversity in political communication is to side with one group against another. However, in the context of a democratic nation such as the Philippines, this may be seen as prioritizing partisan interests over common national interests or negative campaigning. To avoid this, politicians may present an argument in a way that incorporates a range of viewpoints, or present adversarial politics as their own personal *anti-logos*, positioning themselves as above petty squabbles. They may also appeal to shared beliefs to try to unite their audience. Another strategy is to frame the issue in terms of a common enemy, presenting the political project to address a shared problem or threat. This may involve constructing an enemy image, depicting a particular group as the source of the problem, and portraying the political project as the solution. However, this strategy may also be seen as divisive or manipulative. One example of this is constitutive futurity, where it is a strategy in which the object of political address (such as a nation) is projected into an undetermined future, rather than being addressed as a single group in the present. This allows the speaker to speak on behalf of a group that is not yet fully formed or recognized.

A good example of this is through those that are in the center in the world of politics. Political leaders may try to appeal to different audiences by presenting themselves as representatives of a particular group and their political goals as reflecting the values and norms of that group. They may use nonverbal forms of communication, such as their appearance and body language, to show their social identities and affiliations without explicitly stating them. This is known as an implicit identity display, as opposed to an explicit identity avowal, which is a verbal statement of one's identity. These politicians may implicitly show that they are aligned with an audience is by using first-person plural pronouns like "we," "us," and "our," which can signal a sense of unity and shared purpose with the audience. Research has shown that politicians may use these pronouns differently when trying to align themselves with different groups, and that changes in the use of first-person plural pronouns can indicate shifts in political alignment.

Politicians may also use ambiguous language to appeal to multiple, potentially conflicting, groups without changing their position or appearing inconsistent.

Web page of the political party Uniteam, a portmanteau of the words “Unity” and “Team” with the highlight of the word “sama sama” or “together” in the slogan.
(Source: BBM Sara Uniteam Webpage)

Digital rhetoric is the study of how traditional rhetorical techniques, such as *ethos*, *pathos*, and *logos*, are used and adapted in digital media. It also involves examining the characteristics, affordances, and constraints of digital media and their potential for building individual identities and social communities. Digital rhetoric can be connected to the wider field of rhetorical theory, particularly in relation to science and technology. Research has shown that digital media, like computers and the internet, can be used as persuasive technologies, and has examined the ways in which these media can extend and transform traditional concepts of rhetoric as persuasion. However, digital rhetoric also raises ethical issues, such as the manipulation of people through persuasive technology and the potential for biased or misleading information to be amplified in digital spaces. By considering how scientific inquiry takes place in digital environments and how digital platforms support self-expression, participation, and collaboration, we can better understand the potential of digital spaces to foster creative collaborations, build scientific communities, and generate new ideas and research. A theory of digital rhetoric that looks at how traditional methods of persuasion are transformed in digital spaces opens new possibilities for study and a deeper understanding of the role of technology in shaping the rhetoric of science.

Studies of digital communication have identified several key features of communication in online spaces, such as speed, reach, anonymity, and interactivity, which can both enable and shape communication but also raise ethical concerns. Other characteristics of digital media, such as numerical representation, modularity, automation, variability, and transcoding, contribute to its ability to support self-expression, participation, and creative collaboration, but also raise questions about the meaning of terms like "digital" and "interactivity" and the relationship

between authors and readers. These studies have also examined the purposes and outcomes of digital communication, including persuasion, self-expression, and participation and creative collaboration in building communities of shared interests. These interactions, which involve the creation and negotiation of individual and group identities, can be seen akin to the traditional concept of ethos, involving the ongoing performance of identity through social interaction. These interactions also result in the formation of online and offline communities of shared interests, which may cut across demographic differences such as gender, income, age, education, and ethnicity.

To look upon how former President Ferdinand Marcos Sr. presents himself to the country, it is interesting to look upon his inaugural address. In this address that he made, he tackled the challenges faced by the country, presenting a rhetorical situation in which the country is in crisis with corruption, a barren treasury, and demoralized armed forces. The President called for change and national greatness, drawing on the country's history of heroism and patriotism, and appealed to the audience's sense of duty and patriotism. The President also addressed issues such as social and economic transformation, law and order, and corruption.

He also emphasized their commitment to upholding the law and maintaining order and presented a vision of a country with a new approach and a change of pace to address its problems. The President emphasized the importance of economic planning and international relations, particularly with other countries in Asia, and the need for the country to be guided by national interests and to be actively engaged in the cause of freedom. The President appealed to the audience's patriotism and national pride and called on them to work towards a vision of greatness for the country. A vision of progress and transformation for the country is what Marcos Sr. presents to the audience, characterized by agricultural development, industrialization, and increased trade and commerce. The President appealed to the audience's sense of national pride and their shared dream of greatness and called on them to march together towards this shared vision. The President also spoke about the importance of offering all efforts to a higher power and the need to drive oneself to be great.

Well, it is to be expected that in his long reign of rule, he implemented various public works projects that expanded the quality of life for many Filipinos. However, his government was also marked by corruption and abuse of power, involving crony capitalism that had negative consequences for many Filipinos, which have been almost, if not all, related all back to him. In 1972, Marcos declared Martial Law, claiming there was a threat of rebellion from communist and leftist groups. He instigated policies that resulted in increased stability and growth for the Philippine economy. Land reform initiatives also transferred land to farming families. However, Marcos's regime was also pigeon-holed using martial law to silence and relegate opposition, and the enrichment of Marcos and his cronies through the establishment of monopolies and semimonopolies in various industries, including manufacturing, construction, and financial services. This crony capitalism resulted in the diversion of millions of dollars in profits overseas. The military also became steadfast to Marcos and played a significant role in preserving his authoritarian rule.

But in the 80s, Ferdinand Marcos faced growing opposition from various sectors of society, including student activists, religious groups, and labor unions. This opposition was fueled by widespread discontent with Marcos's authoritarian rule, corruption, and abuse of power. In 1986, Marcos was ultimately forced to flee the country after a popular uprising known as the People Power Revolution toppled his regime. Benigno Aquino, a member of the opposition, played a significant role in the fight against Marcos's regime.

Aquino was imprisoned following the declaration of martial law in 1972, but he emerged as a deeper and more committed leader of the democratic opposition during his time in jail. In 1980, Aquino was allowed to go to the United States for medical treatment and became a major leader of the opposition in exile. Despite the dangers of returning to the Philippines, Aquino decided to do so in 1983. The assassination of Aquino at the Manila International Airport in 1983 sparked widespread outrage and protests the Marcos regime. This tragic event became a rallying point for the opposition and ultimately led to the emergence of the People's Power movement, which eventually succeeded in toppling Marcos's regime in 1986. The fall of the regime marked a significant turning point in Philippine politics and marked the end of an era marked by corruption, abuse of power, and authoritarian rule.

The fall of Ferdinand Marcos's government in the Philippines was a result of a collaborative effort by a range of individuals and groups. At the forefront of this was the People's Power movement, a coalition that brought together the Catholic Church, the business community, and some members of the armed forces to oppose the corrupt and authoritarian Marcos regime. This movement was led by Corazon Aquino, the wife of opposition leader Senator Benigno "Ninoy" Aquino, who became a symbol of hope and resistance for many Filipinos who were dissatisfied with the Marcos government. A significant factor in the fall of the regime was the alliance between Aquino and Salvador Laurel, which combined Aquino's widespread popular support with Laurel's organizational skills. This alliance allowed the opposition to mount a strong challenge to the Marcos regime in the presidential election of February 1986. When the election results were falsified in Marcos's favor, the outrage of the opposition and the subsequent People's Power uprising ultimately led to the fall of the Marcos regime and the restoration of democracy in the Philippines.

The Catholic Church, long aligned with the elites in the Philippines, played a significant role in opposing the Marcos regime. Inspired by the pope's commitment to human rights and social justice, the Philippine hierarchy began to openly oppose the regime's abuses following the assassination of Benigno Aquino. The National Movement for Free Elections (NAMFREL), a Catholic lay organization, also played a crucial role in monitoring elections and preventing fraud in the 1984 National Assembly elections and the 1986 presidential election. These efforts by the Catholic Church and NAMFREL contributed to the ultimate downfall of the Marcos regime and the restoration of democracy in the Philippines.

The Reform the Armed Forces Movement (RAM), a group of young military officers committed to professional reform and allied with Minister of National Defense Juan Ponce Enrile, also played a vital role in the fall of the Marcos government. In the latter stages of Marcos's rule, RAM joined forces with the People's Power movement and other opposition

groups to successfully overthrow Marcos and restore democracy in the Philippines. The United States also played a significant role in the fall of the Marcos regime, although its support was not always consistent. Initially, the United States was a key ally of Marcos and provided him with economic and military aid. However, as the regime's corruption and human rights abuses became more apparent, the United States started to distance itself from Marcos and eventually supported the People's Power movement. The combined efforts of these various actors ultimately led to the fall of the Marcos regime and the restoration of democracy in the Philippines.

Following the downfall of Ferdinand Marcos's regime, the People's Power movement, led by Corazon Aquino, implemented reforms aimed at addressing the corruption and abuse of power that had characterized Marcos's rule. These reforms aimed to address the legacy of Marcos's regime and ensure that such corruption and abuse of power would not be repeated in the future. The events of Marcos's rule, including the corruption and abuse of power, continue to be remembered in the Philippines as a cautionary tale. Marcos died in exile in Hawaii in 1989. While his presidency had some positive effects, such as improved infrastructure and economic growth, it was also marked by widespread corruption and abuse of power. These negative aspects of his rule contributed to the decline in popular support for Marcos and ultimately led to his downfall in the 1986 People Power Revolution.

The Philippines continues to grapple with the legacy of the Marcos regime, which imposed martial law for 14 years and was marked by widespread human rights abuses and corruption. In recent years, there have been protests and outrage over the return to power of the Marcos family, with Ferdinand "Bongbong" Marcos Jr. now being the president and his sister Imee Marcos serving as senator. These events have brought the issue of martial law back into the public consciousness and sparked discussions about the dangers of authoritarian rule.

On the other hand, now president Ferdinand Marcos Jr. has consistently tried to whitewash the history of the Marcos regime, downplaying the atrocities committed during the martial law period and making false statements about his family's role in events. In a viral interview with actress Toni Gonzaga, Bongbong Marcos claimed that his father declared martial law due to the threat of communist rebels and secessionists, but many of those arrested and detained under martial law had no connection to these groups and were critics of the Marcos regime. Bongbong Marcos has also denied knowledge of his father's wealth and claimed that the Marcos family had the military advantage during the 1986 People Power Revolution, which is not supported by the experiences and accounts of those who lived through these events.

Considering the recent interview with Toni Gonzaga, the Marcoses are still endeavoring to downplay and deny the atrocities that occurred during Martial Law. Bongbong Marcos's claims that only those involved in illegal activities were arrested and imprisoned, and that the Marcoses had no knowledge of the torture and killings that occurred during this period, are not braced by the accounts of survivors and witnesses or the findings of human rights organizations. This continued denial and revisionism serves only to further devastate the victims and their families and hinders the possibility of reaching justice and closure for them. It is imperative that the truth about Martial Law be recognized and that the Marcoses be held accountable for their

actions. The events of the past must not be neglected and must serve as a keepsake to strive for a better future.

In addition to denying and downplaying the human rights abuses committed during Martial Law, the Marcoses have also been accused of plundering the country's wealth and resources. During their 20-year rule, the Marcoses are believed to have embezzled billions of dollars from the Philippine government and its citizens. This wealth was allegedly used to fund lavish lifestyles, including the purchase of expensive properties and artworks, as well as to finance political campaigns. Despite the evidence against them, the Marcoses have yet to be held accountable for their alleged crimes. In fact, they have successfully regained political power and influence in the Philippines. In 2010, Imee Marcos was elected as governor of Ilocos Norte, and Bongbong Marcos ran for vice president in the 2016 elections.

The reappearance of the Marcos family in the political sphere has caused widespread concern and outrage among those who recall the repressive and abusive nature of their former regime. Many fear a return to authoritarian rule and the erosion of civil liberties, as evidenced by the appointment of retired military generals to government positions and the allocation of funds for targeted attacks on detractors. Some have even suggested that the past administration, led by former President Rodrigo Duterte, is enforcing a "de facto martial law." These actions and the continued influence of the Marcos family have sparked widespread protests and calls for accountability.

It is important that the truth about the Marcoses and their role in the atrocities committed during Martial Law be remembered and recognized. The continued denial and revisionism of their history only serves to further traumatize the victims and their families and hinders the likelihood of achieving justice and closure for them. It is crucial that the Marcoses be held accountable for their actions and that the lessons of the past be remembered to prevent the repetition of such abuses in the future. Only by acknowledging the truth and carrying those responsible accountable can we hope to move forward as a nation and build a better future for all Filipinos.

Output Insights: Third Module

With the group's insight at the third module, we observe the relation of it to Erving Goffman's *The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life*, published in 1959, which examines the various elements of social interactions. Goffman, a member of the Chicago School, uses a symbolic interactionist perspective and a microsociological approach to analyze the individual components of interactive processes, including individual identity, group relations, the impact of the environment, and the movement and meaning of information in interactions. He applies a "dramaturgical approach" to his study, viewing social interactions as performances shaped by the environment and audience, and constructed to present the desired "impressions" to others. Goffman's perspective offers new insights into the nature of social interactions and the psychology of the individual, illustrating how individuals develop their identity or persona through their interactions with others through the exchange of information.

Goffman deals with the nature of group dynamics through a dialogue of "teams" and the relationship concerning performance and audience. He uses the concept of a team to illustrate the work of a group of people who "cooperate" in a performance to achieve goals accepted by the group. Cooperation can take the form of unison in demeanor and behavior or the assumption of various roles by everyone, depending on the desired outcome of the performance. Goffman uses the example of the "shill," a member of the team who serves as a visible model for the audience of the kind of comeback the performers are seeking, as an example of a "discrepant role" in the team. In each case, the individual undertakes a front that is known to enhance the group's routine. The need for everyone to sustain their front to provide for the team performance reduces the possibility of dissent. While the unifying elements of the team are often less complete than the requirements of the performance, actors feel a strong pressure to conform to the anticipated front in the presence of an audience, as deviation can harm the credibility of the entire performance. As a result, misunderstanding is usually carried out in the absence of an audience, where philosophical and performance modifications can be made without the threat of defragmenting the goals of the team or the personality of the individual.

Erving Goffman and his three famous books, and images of former President and dictator Ferdinand Marcos Sr. as an example of audience segregation, a concept brought up by Goffman which separates him from being a family man and a dominant politician. (Sources: Wikipedia, Amazon, Ebay, Amazetify.com, and Imeldamarcos.weebly.com)

The book examines how people present themselves and manage their public image in social interactions. However, the book does not delve deeply into the experiences of marginalized individuals or the role of ritual and ceremony in this process. In his later work, such as *Stigma* and *Interaction Ritual*, Goffman expands on the concept of "face work," which refers to the use of verbal and nonverbal symbols in constructing identity and character. He also discusses the importance of action and risk-taking in defining character, and the role of social spaces in the recreation of the self. Goffman allocates the performance of the team from the audience in terms of "region," based on the relationship between the audience and the performance. He divides region into "front," "back," and "outside" the stage, depending on the proximity of the audience to the performance. While the "official stance" of the team is visible in their frontstage presentation, in the backstage, the impression created by the performance is knowingly contradicted, indicating a more "truthful" type of performance. In the backstage, the conflicts, and disagreements inherent in familiarity are more fully explored, often resulting in a secondary type of presentation, depending on the absence of the responsibilities of the team performance. *Audience segregation* refers to the practice of separating different groups of spectators during a performance. This allows the performers to tailor their presentation to the needs and expectations of each audience and helps to preserve the relationships and social hierarchies within the group or institution hosting the event. Being excluded from the performance means being unable to participate in these dynamics and may result in a feeling of isolation or disconnection from the group.

Roberto Salas Benedicto, a sugar landlord and notable crony of the Marcoses, along with his channels, the Banahaw Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) and the City2 Television.
(Sources: Tita de Bacolod, Mr. JA)

Goffman's work in *The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life* and *Interaction Ritual* examines how people present themselves to others and navigate social interactions. He introduces the concept of the "line," which refers to how people define their identity and character through ritualized actions and symbols, and he discusses the role of nonverbal and verbal symbols in shaping this identity. Goffman also explores the influence of social spaces on identity construction and suggests that people may engage in risky or action-filled activities, such as gambling or bullfighting, to define their character and experience a sense of agency. These ideas can be connected to a larger understanding of society by examining the relationship between the forces that shape society and the individual, and considering the concept of spontaneity, or the expression of a genuine self. To fully understand these concepts, it may be helpful to also consider the perspectives of macrotheorists such as Durkheim and Gramsci. Durkheim's work in *The Division of Labor in Society* addresses the concept of spontaneity, while Gramsci's concept of *hegemony* refers to the unconscious acceptance of social institutions and the role of changes in consciousness in altering this dynamic. Hegemony establishes a "moving equilibrium" through the incorporation of cultural doctrine into common sense and the definition of "idealized" performance, representing the ideas of the ruling class and shaping interpersonal interactions and microsociological phenomena such as face-to-face communication.

Connecting it with the theme of this synthesis, this part will explore the identities brought upon by the father and son duo of the Marcos family. Ferdinand E. Marcos Sr., as we all know, was a former dictator in the Philippines who ruled from 1972 to 1986. During his regime, he used the media to control and manipulate public perception. He arrested and silenced many journalists and critics, shut down numerous newspapers, TV channels, and radio stations, and used his cronies to take over major media companies and establish new ones. Our university's campus in Diliman played a role in resistance to Marcos's media control. After the dictator was deposed in 1986, a shift in the media landscape happened, with an improvement in freedom of expression and the rise of computing. However, the media in the Philippines has faced ongoing challenges, including censorship and government interference.

The legacy of Ferdinand Marcos Sr., while horrible, ended up being edited in a cake.
(Sources: The Independent, Reddit)

Marcos Sr. portrayed himself as a strong and divinely ordained leader who was tasked with bringing prosperity and stability to the Philippines. He used his charisma and wealth, along with his political connections and military power, to maintain his hold on the presidency. He also exploited his relationship with the Catholic Church to rally popular support and silence his opponents, while engaging in acts of corruption and violence that impoverished the nation. To maintain power, he declared martial law and extended his presidential term through bribery and a constitutional convention. He also quelled opposition through arrests, torture, and assassination, including the killing of opposition leader Ninoy Aquino. Despite these efforts, he eventually failed to win a fair and legitimate election in 1986 and was forced to flee the country amid prevalent protests and the interference of the Roman Catholic Church. Even after his exile and death, his legacy has continued to haunt the Philippines, as his family members have returned to positions of power and influence.

An example of a Uniteam supporter page in the social media site Facebook.
(Source: Facebook)

But those were the things of the past, as the new face of the Filipino government is now Ferdinand "Bongbong" Marcos Jr., the son of the former dictator of the Philippines, was recently elected president of the country. The regime of Marcos Jr.'s father was known for a plethora of human rights violations against all Filipinos during that time, and an indicative of oppressive autocracy. However, Marcos Jr. has been able to use a disinformation campaign to try to change the history of his family and improve their image. This campaign has blended elements of myth and nationalism and has been supported by social media influencers and fan cultures. It has been successful in manipulating domestic public opinion and played a significant role in Marcos Jr.'s presidential victory.

Social media platforms have competed to have a role in the restoration of Bongbong Marcos' image and the success of his campaign. The use of social media influencers and fan cultures has allowed the Marcos family to spread their narrative and myths to a large audience, particularly among younger voters. These platforms have provided a space for the Marcos family to present a new version of their history, one that emphasizes their supposed role in bringing prosperity and growth to the country while modulating or denying the abuses perpetrated during the regime. Social media has made it easier for the Marcos family to spread their message to a larger audience because of its wide reach and accessibility. These platforms also use algorithms and data-driven targeting, which allows the Marcos campaign to tailor their messaging to specific demographics that are more likely to support their goals for the country.

While it is true that the tensions between the Philippines and the CPP-NPA-NDF are almost over because of the death of JoMa recently, some people in the comments of VP Sara Duterte still connects the news to the “dumbness” of a defeated candidate, former VP Leni Robredo. (Source: Facebook)

The use of social media platforms in this campaign is representative of the global problem of whether democracy can withstand the influence of technology. The Philippines is not the only country to have faced this issue, as similar tactics have been used in other elections around the world, including in the United States and Brazil. Tech platforms have struggled to combat disinformation that spreads beyond English-speaking countries. There are concerns that with over three dozen determinative national elections occurring in 2022, asymmetry in the capacity to combat disinformation may have a significant impact on the outcomes of these elections. The rehabilitation of the Marcos brand and the use of disinformation in Philippine politics can be traced back to 2014, with the global escalation of informational warfare in the Crimean conflict and the subsequent political impact in 2016 with the elections of Rodrigo Duterte and Donald Trump. The Philippines has been referred to as "patient zero" and a "petri dish" for disinformation by Facebook and Cambridge Analytica, respectively.

A major concern with the use of disinformation in campaigns like the one run by Marcos Jr. is the impact it can have on the democratic process. When voters are offered with false or misleading information, they make decisions based on that information rather than on the facts. It follows that the election of candidates who are not the most qualified or who do not have the best interests of the country at heart. In the case of Marcos Jr., his family's history of human rights abuses and corruption should have disqualified him from consideration for the presidency. However, the successful manipulation of public opinion through disinformation allowed him to win the election despite these issues.

Also, disinforming the crowd in electoral campaigns can contribute to the polarization of society. When people are fed information that supports their preexisting beliefs and biases, it can lead to a further widening of the gap between different groups. This can make it more difficult for people to come together and work towards common goals, leading to a breakdown of trust and cooperation within a society. In the Philippines, the use of disinformation in the campaign of Marcos Jr. may have contributed to the deepening of divisions within the country, making it more difficult for the government to address the challenges it faces.

The last concern to point about disinformation in campaigns is the impact it can have on the credibility and integrity of democratic institutions. When people lose faith in the electoral process, they may become cynical with the concept of democracy and instead follow an autocratic rule, leading to a decline in voter turnout and a decline in trust in government. Nowadays in our country, the use of disinformation in the campaign of Marcos Jr. may have undermined the credibility of the electoral process and damaged the trust of the public in their government. As people living in a democratic country, to ensure that democracy remains firm, it is essential that tech platforms and governments work together to combat disinformation and protect the integrity of the electoral process.

Rey Joseph Nieto, a well-known troll in his alias ThinkingPinoy, bashes a top fan of his Facebook page, whose comment is a form of constructive criticism. (Source: Facebook)

But it is only not the revisions that are facilitated by this “troll army” of the current president must be kept in check and combatted. Big tech platforms and other international organizations must take action to address the issue of disinformation and its impact on democratic processes. Without such efforts, autocrats and would-be autocrats may continue to use these tactics to rewrite their identities and manipulate public opinion in their favor. Overall, tech platforms have provided a powerful tool for the Marcos family to rewrite their identity and present themselves as a viable option for leadership in the Philippines. Without these platforms, it is likely that their efforts to rehabilitate their image would have been much less successful.

However, it is worth noting that Marcos Jr.'s campaign has also been marked using disinformation and the manipulation of public opinion, which can raise question marks above the

heads of people especially about his responsibility to transparency and democratic principles. While he may not be ruling with the same level of brutality as his father did, the use of propaganda and misinformation to win elections is still a threat to the integrity of the democratic process. It will be important for Marcos Jr. to address these issues and demonstrate that he is committed to governing in a fair and transparent manner.

Moreover, Marcos Jr. has taken a more strident stance on the South China Sea dispute than Rodrigo Duterte. While Duterte adopted a more conciliatory approach towards China, Marcos has emphasized the importance of the Philippines' sovereignty and territorial rights. In his first State of the Nation Address, Marcos declared that the country's sovereignty is "sacred" and vowed not to allow "a single square millimetre" of its maritime rights to be trampled upon. In contrast to Duterte, who referred to the 2016 tribunal ruling against China's claims in the South China Sea as a "piece of paper," Marcos has described the ruling as "very important" and a tool for the Philippines to assert its territorial rights. Despite Marcos' harder stance on the South China Sea dispute, China remains an important partner of the Philippines both economically and politically. The ties between the Marcoses and China stretch back to 1975, when the Philippines was one of the first US treaty allies to formalize diplomatic relations with China. At the same time, he also adopted a friendlier approach to the United States than Duterte and has welcomed the prospect of expanded trade ties with the US.

Along with the South China Sea dispute, there are several other issues that will likely shape the relationship between the Philippines and China under the leadership of Marcos Jr. These include economic cooperation, particularly in areas such as infrastructure development and trade, as well as cultural and people-to-people exchanges. As China continues to play an increasingly dominant role in the region, it will be important for the Philippines to meticulously manage its relations with its neighbor to take advantage of the benefits for the country and its people. Marcos will have to navigate a delicate balancing act to sustain good relations with China while also standing up for the country's sovereignty and interests.

The relationship between the Philippines and China under Marcos' leadership will likely be characterized by both cooperation and competition, with both sides seeking to advance their own agendas while also working together on issues of mutual concern. Generally, it seems that he attempts to pursue a more balanced approach to foreign relations, enhancing the Philippines' strategic capital by maintaining good relations with all major powers. His hardening rhetoric on China is likely to be more tactical than strategic, meant in part to reassure Western allies who were concerned about Duterte's pivot towards China at the expense of traditional partners. However, it remains to be seen how Marcos' approach will play out, and whether he will be able to successfully navigate the complex dynamics of the region.

To conclude, while Bongbong is the spawn of Marcos Sr., he has not necessarily followed in his father's footsteps in terms of his leadership style and policies. Marcos Sr. was known for ruling the country with an iron fist, using his power to suppress dissent and exert control over the population. He suspended basic rights, tortured, and slaughtered thousands of Filipinos, and engaged in widespread corruption during his time in office. In contrast, Bongbong Marcos has presented himself as a more moderate and reform-oriented leader. He has focused his campaign

on issues such as job creation, education, and infrastructure development, and has sought to distance himself from the more controversial aspects of his family's history. While it is still too early to say what kind of leader Marcos Jr. will be, he currently strives to create a path of an approach to governing than his father did.

Bongbong Marcos meets Xi Jinping. (Source: The Manila Times)

Output Insights: Fourth Module

For the fourth module, as a group, we understood the importance of representation in communication. We have learned that representation allows for the creation and interpretation in various forms of communication, such as media and popular culture and it plays a role in the production and propagation of culture, as they are depicted to influence the values, beliefs, and norms of a culture. However, we have also learned that representation is not a neutral process and can be influenced by power dynamics and social hierarchies. This has led us to acknowledge the need to think about the ways in which interpretation can have an impact on cultural values along with ways in which it can argue with dominant ideologies. As a group, we have been reflecting on the work of Stuart Hall which was presented by Al Jazeera on the social media platform site YouTube. Hall is a media theorist who focused on representation in cultural studies. He was particularly interested in the constructionist approach, which suggests that meaning is not fixed or pre-existing, but rather is constructed through language and cultural context. This approach challenges the traditional view of representation as a simple reflection of reality and instead sees it as a dynamic and culturally mediated process.

Hall was also interested in the power of mainstream media in representing various aspects of society, such as race, gender, class, ethnicity, and religion. He argued that media are not neutral, but rather convey ideologies that can be exposed and critiqued by media theorists. He rejected the idea that audiences are passive receivers of media messages and instead proposed that they may accept, negotiate, or reject these messages. Hall encouraged seeking out alternative stories and perspectives from lesser-known or marginalized media sources to gain a complete understanding of society. The group also learned about the different approaches to understanding the process of representation. There is the reflective approach, which holds that the meaning of an object or event lies in the real world and language simply reflects this meaning. Language is used to impose meaning on the world and is shaped by social and cultural practices. Meaning is constructed using representative systems like concepts and signs and is essential in the study of culture as it permits individuals to share a common perspective and communicate effectively. Representation also plays a role in the production and reproduction of culture through the creation and interpretation of meaning in communication.

In the constructionist approach, the semiotic and discursive models both emphasize the influence of language and cultural context on the meanings produced and exchanged within a culture. Effective communication and meaning exchange require shared understanding of signs and symbols and a shared conceptual and linguistic system. The relationship between signs, concepts, and objects they represent can be complex and influenced by context, and the meaning of a sign may be open to interpretation. These approaches were influenced by the works of Ferdinand de Saussure's theories of language and meaning, as discussed in the reading.

Saussure argued that language is a system of signs made up of a signifier (the form, such as a word or image) and a signified (the concept in the mind associated with the form). He also introduced the concepts of language, the underlying structure and rules of language, and parole, the individual act of speaking or writing. This structuralist approach, which emphasizes the underlying codes and structures that shape cultural phenomena, has been widely applied in the field of semiotics, the study of signs and symbols in culture and how they communicate meaning. Semiotics views culture as a sort of "language" that can be analyzed using linguistic concepts such as signifiers, signifieds, and codes. The semiotic approach has been used to study various cultural phenomena, including fashion, media, and popular culture. Critics have argued that Saussure's model fails to account for the historical and cultural context in which language is used and oversimplifies the process of meaning-making.

In the reading, the example that is given is in the context of fashion, clothes serve as signifiers that represent certain concepts or signifieds, such as elegance or casualness. These signifiers are linked to concepts through a basic code that is based on the fashion code of western consumer cultures, which may vary based on factors like gender, age, class, and race. The meaning conveyed by fashion is created through the arrangement of signifiers in a particular sequence and in relation to one another, and this meaning may be interpreted differently by those who share the same fashion code. The process of representation in fashion involves two linked operations: the basic code that links a particular piece of clothing with a concept, and the fashion system that arranges the signifiers in a specific way to convey a specific meaning or message.

Fashion can also be used as a form of communication and expression, allowing individuals to convey their identity, status, and cultural affiliations through their clothing choices.

During the Marcos regime in the Philippines, thousands of people were subjected to brutal torture methods to extract information, punish dissent, and intimidate the population. These methods included electric shock, the "San Juanico Bridge" technique, truth serum injections, Russian roulette, beating, pistol-whipping, water cure, strangulation, cigar and flat iron burns, pepper torture, animal treatment, solitary confinement and isolation, and threats of harm to families. The regime also targeted specific groups, such as ethnic minorities, labor unions, and student activists, for particularly harsh treatment, including torture and imprisonment.

Different torture methods during the Martial Law period. (Source: Rappler)

The use of torture by the Marcos regime was a gross violation of human rights and had a lasting impact on the victims and their families. It is important to remember and learn from this dark period in Philippine history to ensure that such atrocities are never repeated. It is crucial to hold accountable those who perpetrated these crimes and to work towards a society that values and protects the fundamental rights of all individuals. One way that people can remember and honor the victims of torture during the Marcos regime is by supporting efforts to hold those responsible accountable for their actions. This includes supporting class action lawsuits, such as the one mentioned in the text, which seek to seek justice and reparations for the victims and their

families. It also means supporting organizations and initiatives that work to promote human rights and prevent torture in the present day.

The events of the Marcos regime and the subsequent restoration of democracy in the Philippines continue to be a significant and controversial topic in the country. The regime, led by Ferdinand Marcos, is remembered for its widespread human rights violations and abuse of power, including the use of torture and other atrocities against those who opposed the government. The restoration of democracy following the 1986 People Power Revolution was a crucial moment in the country's history, but the return of the Marcoses to power in recent years has sparked outrage and concern among those who fear a return to authoritarian rule.

The Marcoses' ongoing denial and revisionism of the atrocities executed during Martial Law is truly disturbing and offensive to the victims and their families. President Bongbong Marcos has again and again lied about the reasons for his father's declaration of martial law and downplayed the human rights violations that occurred during this time. His statements and actions are a blatant attempt to sanitize the history of the Marcos regime and avoid being held accountable for their actions. It is vital that the truth about the Marcos regime and the crimes committed during Martial Law be recognized, and that the Marcoses be held liable for their actions. This includes helping efforts to bring perpetrators to justice, such as class action lawsuits, and supporting organizations that stand for human rights and prevent torture.

Furthermore, taking action to support victims and prevent torture, it is important for people to educate themselves about these events and their significance. By learning about the impacts of authoritarian regimes and the importance of defending human rights, people can be more equipped to recognize and stand up to similar abuses of power in the future. The legacy of the Marcos regime and its use of torture serves as a reminder of the devastating consequences of authoritarian rule. It is up to all of us to remember the victims and to work towards a future where such atrocities are never allowed to happen again. Remembering and honoring the victims and their struggles is a critical part of this process, and it is essential that their memory and legacy be preserved for future generations.

The other side of the story in connection to the representations of the Martial Law era is the love for freedom, which is spearheaded by the representation of the “Yellow Ribbon” a powerful symbol of democracy and resistance in the Philippines. It gained prominence during the 1970s as a symbol of support for Benigno Aquino Jr., who was assassinated upon his return from exile in 1983. The Yellow Ribbon became a global symbol of people power and resistance to authoritarian rule during the 1986 People Power Revolution, which ended the Marcos dictatorship and saw the rise of Corazon Aquino to the presidency. In recent years, the Yellow Ribbon has also been used to show support for Corazon Aquino during her battle with colon cancer and for her son, former President Benigno Aquino III, during his presidency. The Yellow Ribbon is a widely recognized symbol in the Philippines and around the world, with many people displaying it on their homes, cars, and social media pages.

Through the electoral campaign of former President Noynoy Aquino, the Yellow Ribbon fever has not only spread online, but it has also inspired people to take physical action in support of the former President. In the Philippines, people have been tying Yellow Ribbons around trees

and posts as a symbol of their support for Corazon Aquino, who has recently died during that time. The Yellow Ribbon movement represents the fight for freedom and democracy, and it serves as a reminder of the sacrifices that Mrs. Aquino and others made to bring about positive change in the Philippines. It is an important symbol for future generations to remember and reflect upon, as it serves as a reminder of the struggles and triumphs that have shaped the country's history.

The “Yellow Ribbon” has a global significance, representing hope and a call to action for those fighting for their rights and freedoms around the world. It serves as a reminder that it is our collective responsibility to work towards a better future and to never give up on the fight for democracy and human rights. In the Philippines, the Yellow Ribbon holds a special meaning, symbolizing the sacrifices made by the Aquino family in the fight for democracy and serving as a reminder to future generations to stand up for their rights and fight for a better future. With a history of authoritarian rule, the Yellow Ribbon stands as a symbol of resilience and resistance, urging us to never give up the fight for freedom and justice.

The Yellow Ribbon support for the Aquino family, particularly that of the movement brought on by former President Cory Aquino. (Source: Twibbon)

Output Insights: Fifth Module

The fifth module explores the role of history, power, and global institutions in shaping intercultural communication and encourages readers to engage in a process of learning and reflection. The concept of culture has a complicated history, often being used to stratify people, and justify colonization, but over time, struggles within academia and society have led to a more inclusive understanding of culture. The book discusses the importance of considering positionality, or the social and cultural factors that shape our experiences and perspectives, in

studying and practicing intercultural communication. It also introduces the concept of ethnocentrism, or the tendency to view one's own culture as superior, and the importance of overcoming this in order to effectively communicate with people from other cultures. The book also emphasizes the need for intercultural praxis, or the integration of theory and practice in addressing intercultural communication issues.

Culture is often defined as a system of shared meanings passed down through generations and expressed through symbols. However, a cultural studies perspective views culture as a site of contestation where meanings are constantly negotiated and influenced by power dynamics. From this perspective, culture is seen as an apparatus of power that operates through hegemony, or the acceptance of dominant ideas and interests. Cultural studies also emphasize the agency of individuals and groups in producing, challenging, and negotiating meanings within culture. Culture is not only shaped by historical and political forces, but also by economic, technological, and media factors. Therefore, it is important to consider the cultural influences on communication and to be aware of one's own cultural perspective in intercultural communication.

One important part of the readings is the idea of positionality, which refers to the idea that an individual's social and power relations influence their perspective and understanding of the world. **Standpoint theory**, which is related to positionality, suggests that people from marginalized or oppressed groups have a unique perspective that can provide a more comprehensive view of the world. This theory is based on the idea that those who are oppressed or subordinated must understand both their own perspective and the perspective of those in power in order to survive. Standpoint theory also emphasizes the connection between power and knowledge, and the potential for marginalized groups to challenge and oppose systems of oppression through their unique perspective. An understanding of positionality can be useful in intercultural communication in order to recognize and avoid the negative effects of ethnocentrism, which is the belief that one's own group is superior to others and can lead to prejudice, discrimination, and violence.

Another is that of the **intercultural praxis**. This is a process of critical, reflective thinking and action that enables individuals to navigate complex intercultural spaces. It involves six elements: inquiry, framing, positioning, dialogue, reflection, and action. Inquiry involves a desire and willingness to learn about and understand others who are different from oneself. Framing refers to the way we interpret and make sense of our intercultural experiences. Positioning refers to the social and power relations that influence our perspective and understanding of the world. Dialogue involves communication and interaction with others in order to exchange ideas and understand different viewpoints. Reflection involves thinking about and analyzing one's intercultural experiences to gain greater awareness and understanding. Action involves taking socially responsible actions in relation to intercultural interactions in the context of globalization. Engaging in intercultural praxis can help individuals to navigate intercultural spaces and increase their critical analysis and social responsibility.

These concepts can be related uniquely in a Filipino context. Communication in Filipino culture is characterized by a strong emphasis on personal connections and socializing in group

settings. Filipinos engage in a lot of questioning and conversation as a way of getting to know each other and establishing context, a concept known as "contexting." Boundaries between public and private matters can be blurry in the Philippines, as there is not a strong concept of privacy. As a result, information that is intended to be private may be disclosed to a larger audience. Gossip and the disclosure of sensitive information are common in Filipino culture, and various words and phrases, such as "*gossip*," "*flag*," and "*verbalization*," are used to refer to these practices.

Informal messengers, such as town criers, are still present in Filipino culture and play a role in the spread of news and personal messages. Communication in the Philippines is often personal in nature, with personal messages and appeals included in formal media settings. Words and phrases related to the sharing of news and opinions, such as "*reveal*," "*report*," and "*inform*," are commonly used. Debating and exchanging opinions is also a tradition in Filipino culture, and the practice of "*balagatasan*," or poetic argument, is prevalent. Words and phrases related to arguing and exchanging opinions, such as "*balitaktan*," "*condemnation*," and "*taltalan-labo-labong*," are commonly used in this context.

The influence of social factors on communication has been a topic of significant interest in recent years, particularly in the context of a culturally diverse society. One key aspect of this topic is the distinction between "*others*" and "*non-others*," and the different ways in which people interact with each other depending on their social status and power dynamics. For example, language use can be a marker of social status and power, with certain languages, such as English, being seen as more prestigious or powerful than others.

The use of nonverbal communication, such as body language and gestures, is also an important aspect of expressive communication. This is particularly evident in the context of Filipino culture, where elegant and rhythmic body movements are a common feature of communication. There have also been studies on the use of signaling systems in communication, such as eye movements, facial expressions, and touch. However, the use of body movement can also be problematic in certain contexts, such as the covert sexual harassment of women through actions such as over-squeezing or patting the shoulder to attract attention, known as "*paninilbihan*."

Cultural differences also play a role in the concept of personal space in communication. Different cultures have different ideas about the appropriate distance for comfortable conversation, with Latinos tending to prefer closer conversations and Americans tending to prefer more distance. These cultural differences can be observed in the way people use space during conversation, with Latinos being more comfortable with being close to the interlocutor and Americans tending to keep a greater distance. Based on observations of cultural practices, it seems that people in certain cultures may be more similar to Latinos in their use of space during communication.

After cultural differences, cognitive differences can also play a role in communication. For example, the concept of "*unay*," which is a native estimation of time based on the flow of events, contrasts with the concept of time as a mechanical clockwork. Additionally, some people may be more inclined towards linear, logical thinking, while others are more skilled in creative

thinking and using mental imagery. These differences can affect the way people communicate, with some tending towards more technical language and abstract thinking, while others are more likely to use metaphors and improvisation. In conclusion, social factors, cultural differences, and cognitive differences all play a significant role in how people communicate with each other. Understanding these influences can help us better navigate the complexities of communication in a diverse society.

In connection to what happened during the Martial Law period in the Philippines, it is imperative that we start first with martial law being declared by President Ferdinand Marcos in 1972, amidst growing opposition to his authoritarian rule and allegations of corruption. This refers to the suspension of civil liberties and the imposition of military rule in a country, usually in times of emergency or conflict. Marcos Sr. at that time asserted that martial law was needed to quell a communist insurgency, but it was widely seen as a way for him to maintain control and suppress political opposition. While massive infrastructure projects were done during his rule, these were often seen as a way for him and his cronies to enrich themselves through kickbacks. The collapse of the Philippine economy under Marcos' leadership contributed to the rise of overseas work as a means for Filipinos to seek a better future for themselves and their families. The legacy of Marcos' martial law regime remains a deeply divisive and painful topic for many Filipinos, particularly those who suffered under his authoritarian rule.

Before the massive rally done by the supporters of Ninoy and subsequently, the presidency of Cory, there are organizations, such as the Lapiang Malaya movement, which was a political and religious organization that formed in the Philippines in the 1940s. In May 1967, their leader called for Marcos Sr. to resign and for a government formed by their movement to take over. A demonstration at their headquarters in Pasay City turned violent, with 32 members of Lapiang Malaya being killed and over 300 more arrested. The Philippine Constabulary later claimed that the group was linked to communism to justify their actions. In the 1960s, the Philippines faced increasing poverty, government debt, and questions about US involvement in the country's economy and the presence of military bases. Protests and demonstrations, often involving student movements, labor groups, and peasant organizations, broke out in response to these issues. These demonstrations were frequently met with police harassment or violence. The calls for a constitutional convention to revise the 1935 Constitution grew louder due to the increasing discontent in society. In 1969, Ferdinand Marcos Sr. was reelected as President. In 1970, a rally outside of his State of the Nation address calling for a non-partisan constitutional convention turned violent when security forces used what some considered excessive force to disperse the protesters. This event, along with several other protests and rallies in the first quarter of 1970, is known as the First Quarter Storm. The protests focused on police brutality and repression and often involved students, workers, peasants, urban poor, drivers, and other sectors.

The following year, students and jeepney drivers struck against rising oil prices. The demonstration at the University of the Philippines turned violent when a professor attempted to disperse the students and was met with resistance. He responded by opening fire on the students, killing one and injuring at least one more. This incident, known as the Diliman Commune, resulted in a standoff between students and police and military forces. The barricades were eventually taken down in exchange for several demands, including a gasoline price rollback and

the withdrawal of military forces from the campus. Eventually, all these events will be remembered as the first flares that burned through the rose-colored lenses of lies by the Marcoses. The Marcoses will be then kicked out in 1986, starting a new age for Filipinos.

In a sense, these events spiraled out a domino effect, causing communication against the opposition to be gravely punished, which is not a trait of democracy. But this case did not stop Filipinos from uniting together to stop what is happening during that time. Even though the Marcoses have returned to the Malacañang, the protests about Martial Law have not stopped. Many protesters against the return of the dictator's family expressed their concern about the existence of a "de facto martial law" under the last administration, citing the appointment of retired military generals to government positions and the allocation of funds for sustained attacks on critics. Some even argued that the pandemic is being used by the Duterte administration to suppress basic civil liberties, such as freedom of expression. These protests and statements demonstrate that the events of Martial Law are still remembered and opposed by many in the Philippines. While Bongbong Marcos doesn't show signs of emulating his or even Duterte's rule, many people who have been survivors of Martial Law feel dread about even thinking about him being there in the first place.

The government of the Philippines during the period of Marcos Sr's rule was characterized by corruption, human rights abuses, and the displacement of many Filipino elites. Marcos and his associates were accused of using their positions of power to enrich themselves at the expense of the Philippine economy. The government was also known for its use of summary executions, or "salvaging," to silence critics and opponents. Despite the widespread human rights violations and suppression of dissent that occurred during martial law in the Philippines, President Rodrigo Duterte recently suggested that the two children of the Marcoses, Imee and Bongbong, should not be held accountable for the actions of their parents because they were too young at the time. It is crucial to hold those who were complicit in the crimes of the Marcos regime accountable, rather than absolving them based on their age or relationship to the former dictator.

Fast forward to three decades, and the commemoration of the declaration of martial law in the Philippines is an annual event that serves as a reminder of the atrocities and abuses committed during the Marcos dictatorship. It is also an opportunity for the people to reaffirm their commitment to the defense of human rights and democracy, and to resist all forms of repression and tyranny. But now it stopped. This is because the current President of the Philippines, Bongbong Marcos, has attempted to weaken the memories of the human rights violations and atrocities committed during the martial law period of his family's rule and shift the blame onto those who "write history." He has denied any wrongdoing or knowledge of the human rights violations committed during his family's rule and has even claimed that martial law was necessary due to the "wars" the Philippines was fighting against the Communist Party of the Philippines and the secessionist movement in the south. The regime was responsible for widespread human rights violations, including the imprisonment and torture of tens of thousands of people and the killing of over 3,000 individuals. In addition, Bongbong Marcos has recently given an interview with his chief legal counsel, Juan Ponce Enrile, who served as the Martial

Law administrator under Marcos Sr. and was a key figure in the 1986 People Power Revolution that toppled the Marcos regime

It is important to acknowledge and remember the atrocities committed during martial law in the Philippines, including the detention and torture of innocent people and the censorship of the press. The Marcos family, including Imee and Bongbong, have never taken responsibility for their actions and continue to benefit from their ill-gotten wealth. President Duterte's comments absolving them only reinforce this impunity and revision of history. It is crucial for the country to confront and acknowledge these crimes to move forward and prevent them from happening again. A vote that is given for Bongbong Marcos means not only condoning the actions of the past, but also risking a return to that dark chapter in Philippine history.

The fact that Marcos can garner support from some voters, particularly those who were not directly affected by martial law, is a testament to the power of propaganda and revisionist history. Many of these supporters have chosen to forget or ignore the suffering of the martial law victims, instead focusing on the perceived accomplishments of the Marcos regime. This is a dangerous mindset, as it allows for the perpetuation of lies and the continuation of a cycle of abuse and corruption. Those who chose to vote for Bongbong Marcos is not just a decision about one individual, but a choice about the kind of society we want to live in. Do we want to continue to allow those in power to deceive and manipulate us, or do we want a society that values truth, accountability, and justice? The atrocities and corruption of the Marcos regime are well-documented and cannot be denied. By choosing to ignore these actions and instead focus on a revisionist history, Bongbong Marcos is showing that he is not fit to hold public office.

Conclusions

"He who controls information controls the world." This quote by Dr. Stephen Franklin best describes the reign of the two Marcoses in the past, and now in the present. They controlled the country by controlling the media of information and spreading false information to deceive their fellow Filipino people into believing in them. In the past, the regime of former President Ferdinand Marcos Sr. controlled the different media outlets and spread false information to the public. In the current society under the reign of his son, President Ferdinand Marcos Jr., the truth was distorted to the public and false information was spread through different social media platforms. But their scheme of continuous deception of the public has to stop.

To avoid being swayed by misinformation or bias, it is crucial that the public exercise caution and skepticism when consuming information from uncredited sources, particularly those found on social media. Instead of blindly accepting such information as true, it is essential to verify its reliability and carefully evaluate the credibility of the source. Along with this, it is also pivotal to seek out multiple sources of information and conduct thorough research on the topic in question. By taking these steps, we can protect ourselves from being misled by false narratives and ensure that our understanding of the issue is based on factual, reliable information.

Aside from that, we shouldn't be easily convinced by political statements. The main objective of political speech is to get the corresponding effect through persuasion. Politicians wish to increase people's interest and to strengthen their image, to make people share their

opinions and agree with their ideas to inform the general public of their ideology and message. We must develop the ability to validate the information and determine whether sources are reliable enough to disseminate information on a subject. We should know whether they are only saying things for their own benefit or for the country.

As Filipino citizens and students of the University of the Philippines, we must fight for our country. Hence, during this time wherein the Philippines is not only threatened by the spread of the COVID-19 virus, but also by the false information being spread on different media platforms, we should fight against oppression and tyranny and amplify the voices of the people that do not have to fight injustices.

In addition, we students participate in the fight for justice on the ground as members of the University of the Philippines community. We want to combat the pervasive deception and historical revisionism in our neighborhood and put an end to red-tagging in addition to supporting Leni Robredo, who most students are familiar with and who has excellent credentials, skills, and a desire to serve the people.

Implication

The younger generation of Filipinos has the potential to make a real difference in their country by holding those in power accountable and demanding transparency and integrity. This requires a willingness to critically evaluate information and to not be swayed by false narratives or empty promises. One way to do this is by verifying facts and seeking out multiple sources of information, rather than relying on a single perspective or viewpoint. By doing so, individuals can gain a nuanced and truthful insight of the issues facing the country and be better furnished to promote for change.

Besides, it is important for the young ones to vigorously engage in the political process and make their voices heard. This can involve participating in protests or demonstrations, writing letters, or making phone calls to elected officials, or running for office themselves. The new generation of Filipinos must work in partnership with others who share their values and goals. By building networks of support and working together towards shared objectives, the younger generation can be more effective in bringing about positive change in their country.

Ultimately, this new generation, including our group, has a unique opportunity to shape the future of the Philippines and to create a better future for all Filipinos. By challenging the norms, standing up for what they believe in and holding those in power accountable, everyone, including us, can help to create a more just and equitable society for all.

Recommendation

In order to gain a deeper understanding of the state of our society, it is essential to view communication from a critical perspective. By doing so, individuals will be able to analyze the ways in which traditional media has spread instances of deception in the past, and how this is like the dissemination of disinformation through new media in the present. Additionally, they will be able to observe how public political comments are crafted to influence listeners to

support certain positions, and how communication impacts them personally, as well as their culture and community.

Furthermore, by engaging in these activities, individuals will be able to identify pressing concerns in society, pinpoint areas of agreement for action, and develop a sense of identity and engagement that will enable them to take meaningful action on behalf of society.

One key objective of our synthesis paper is to delve into the evolving landscape of communication from the martial law period of the Marcos administration until the present, including the shifting processes of mass communication and media convergence. Another objective is to examine the ways in which the Marcos administration and its supporters utilized persuasion techniques, such as ethos, logos, and pathos, to win votes and garner support. Additionally, it is important to study the representation of the Marcos administration and related issues in both traditional and social media, to recognize the ways in which these sources shape public perception.

It is critical to consider the role of intercultural communication and verbal and nonverbal communication in the context of local and global forces that influence intercultural interactions, including history, way of life, experiences, and social and political positions. By considering these factors, individuals will be able to gain a richer understanding of the complexities of communication and its impact on society.

As a society, Filipinos need to use communication as a tool to combat the negative effects of disinformation. Disinformation, or the intentional spread of false or misleading information, has become a pervasive problem in the Philippines, with traditional and social media being used as platforms to spread lies and sow confusion. This has had serious consequences for the nation, including the erosion of trust in institutions and leaders, the proliferation of conspiracy theories, and the undermining of public health efforts during the COVID-19 pandemic.

There are a lot of ways our countrymen can do this, one is by becoming more discerning consumers of information. This means being skeptical of sensational or sensationalized headlines, checking the sources of information, and verifying claims through multiple sources. It also means being aware of one's own biases and being open to hearing different viewpoints. By being more critical in the way they consume information, Filipinos can help to reduce the spread of disinformation and promote a more informed and engaged citizenry.

Another way is to utilize communication to combat disinformation is by being more proactive in their own communication. This can include fact-checking and debunking false or misleading information when it is encountered and sharing accurate and reliable information with others. It can also involve engaging in respectful and constructive dialogue with others, even those with whom one disagrees, in order to promote greater understanding and collaboration. By taking these actions, Filipinos can help to create a more informed and civil society.

Lastly, every one of us needs to combat disinformation by supporting media literacy initiatives and holding those who spread disinformation accountable. This can involve supporting journalism that is accurate, fair, and independent, and calling out those who spread false or misleading information. It can also involve supporting media literacy programs that help individuals develop the skills and knowledge they need to become more discerning consumers of information. Partaking into said actions, every Filipino will have a contribution to a more informed and accountable society.

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